

Heritage Used For Worship Under The Vietnamese Civil Law - Some Defects And Recommendations

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ABSTRACT: The provisions of Vietnamese civil law on heritage used for worship are quite unique compared to the civil laws of the majority of countries. However, the provisions of law on heritage used for worship are still very sketchy, not enough to regulate all the issues arising in this field and at the same time there are still some limitations and inadequacies. This article focuses on the provisions of Vietnamese civil law on heritage used for worship. Based on pointing out the limitations and inadequacies in legal provisions and law enforcement practices, the article makes some recommendations to improve Vietnamese legal provisions on heritage used for worship.

Keywords: Inheritance; heritage of worship; inheritance; heir.

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1. Introduction

To understand the concept of inheritance for worship, we must first understand the concept of inheritance and the concept of worship. From a legal perspective, an inheritance is the property left by the deceased, including the deceased's personal property and the deceased's common property in the common property with others. Thus, when a person is alive, his or her property is called property and after death, the property left by the deceased is called inheritance. The deceased's inheritance will, in principle, be divided among the heirs after the deceased has paid the property obligations.

Worshipping the dead is a long-standing folk belief of the Vietnamese people. Worship is the act of the living performing rituals to commemorate the deceased such as praying, burning incense and performing other rituals. Worshipping the dead is a good tradition, helping to educate the living to be grateful to the deceased, demonstrating the morality of "remembering the source of water when drinking", and at the same time contributing to strengthening solidarity among family members and clans. To worship, there must be a place of worship and items to perform the worship ritual. Therefore, setting aside a part of the family's assets to worship ancestors is a custom that has been deeply ingrained in the traditional lifestyle of our people. From the above situation, it can be affirmed that Vietnamese civil law allows the testator to have the right to set aside a part of the inheritance for worship, which is in line with the cultural traditions and customs in Vietnam.

Thus, it can be understood that the heritage used for worship is the property left by the deceased but not divided to the heirs but to serve the worship. Because the heritage of worship is a cultural practice, a relationship between the living and the deceased, the legal systems that we know do not consider this a scope of law. We have not seen any legal system in foreign countries that has regulations on heritage used for worship. On the contrary, heritage used for worship has been regulated by law for a long time in Vietnam and the old laws called it "incense". Nowadays, heritage used for worship is regulated in Clause 3, Article 626 and Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015.

2. Current status of regulations of Vietnamese civil law on heritage used for worship

2.1. Basis for the origin of worship heritage

According to the provisions of the Civil Code 2015 and judicial practice in Vietnam, inheritance used for worship arises based on the following grounds:

Firstly, the inheritance used for worship arises according to the will of the person leaving the inheritance. The owner of the property has the right to freely make a will to dispose of his property after death, including the right to reserve a part of the inheritance for worship. Therefore, Clause 3, Article 626 of the Civil Code 2015 stipulates that one of the rights of the testator is to reserve a part of the inheritance for bequest and worship. Next, Clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015 also stipulates that in case the testator leaves a part of the inheritance for worship, that part of the inheritance shall not be divided and handed over to the person designated in the will to manage and carry out the worship. Thus, "no one is forced to set aside a part of the inheritance for worship" (Nguyen Van Cu and Tran Thi Hue, 2017). Whether or not the testator reserves a part of the inheritance for worship is entirely up to the will of the testator.

However, it should be noted that according to the Civil Code 2015, the right to freely decide to reserve a part of the inheritance for worship purposes will be limited in certain cases. Specifically, according to Clause 2, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015, in cases where the entire estate of the deceased is not enough to pay his or her property obligations, a part of the inheritance cannot be reserved for worship purposes. This means that if the property obligations of the deceased are larger than the entire estate left by that person, even if the will has reserved a part of the inheritance for worship purposes, it cannot be implemented according to that division (Nguyen Van Huy, 2017). The above provision is consistent with practice, aiming to prevent testators from taking advantage of the provision on the right to reserve a part of the inheritance for worship purposes to avoid fulfilling their obligations to others, thereby contributing to protecting the rights and legitimate interests of the deceased's creditors.

Second, the inheritance of worship arises according to the will of the heir. In practice, it is not uncommon for the testator to leave no will but the heirs agree to reserve a portion of the inheritance for worship and this is also accepted by the Court (Do Van Dai, 2019). The above practice is consistent with the principles of civil law. Because when participating in civil relations, the subjects have the right to freely and voluntarily commit and agree. Any

commitment or agreement that does not violate the prohibitions of the law or is not contrary to social ethics is effective for the parties and must be respected by other subjects (Clause 2, Article 3 of the Civil Code 2015). Thus, the inheritance of worship can arise based on the decision of the co-heirs, even in cases where the deceased did not leave a will.

2.2. Management of heritage used for worship

The worship heritage exists for a long time and can be passed down through many generations. Therefore, to avoid the loss or damage of the worship heritage, there must be a person to manage the worship heritage. In case the testator designates a person to manage the worship heritage, the person to manage the worship heritage is determined according to the will (Clause 3, Article 626 and Clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015). The testator can designate anyone to manage the worship heritage regardless of the marital or blood relationship with the person leaving the heritage. However, usually the person to manage the worship heritage will be someone who has a close blood relationship with the person leaving the heritage.

In case the person appointed to manage the worship estate fails to properly execute the will or does not comply with the agreement of the heirs, the heirs have the right to assign the portion of the estate used for worship to another person to manage for worship. In case the person leaving the estate designates the portion of the estate used for worship but does not appoint a person to manage the worship estate, the heirs shall appoint a person to manage the worship estate.

Paragraph 3, Clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015 also stipulates that in the event that all heirs according to the will have died, the portion of the inheritance used for worship belongs to the person who is legally managing the inheritance among those who are entitled to inherit according to law. There is a problem that the phrase "belonging to" here can be understood as belonging to the ownership of the person who is legally managing the inheritance of worship or only belonging to the management and use of the inheritance of worship. This issue needs to be specifically regulated by law (Hoang The Lien, 2013). We believe that, based on the purpose of the provisions on inheritance used for worship, it can be seen that the phrase "belonging to the person who is legally managing" mentioned above cannot be understood as belonging to the ownership of the person who is legally managing the inheritance of worship. The phrase "belonging to the person who is legally managing" needs to be understood as belonging to the management of the person who is legally managing the inheritance of worship. The person who is legally managing the worship heritage will continue to manage and use it for worship purposes. The person managing the worship heritage has the obligation to look after and preserve the heritage used for worship to avoid loss or damage to the heritage used for worship. The person managing the worship heritage is not allowed to sell, exchange, give away, pledge, mortgage or dispose of the heritage used for worship in any other way.

3. Limitations and shortcomings in Vietnamese civil law regarding heritage used for worship

Through studying the regulations on heritage used for worship in the Civil Code 2015, we found that there are still some limitations and problems as follows:

Firstly, the subjects who have the right to participate in the agreement to appoint an estate manager as stipulated in the Civil Code 2015 are not really clear, leading to many different interpretations: Specifically, according to paragraph 2, clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015: "In case the person leaving the inheritance does not appoint an administrator of the worship estate, the heirs shall agree to appoint an administrator of the worship estate". According to the Civil Code 2015, heirs include testamentary heirs, legal heirs, and heirs according to other provisions (Le Minh Hung, 2020). Thus, the phrase "heirs" is understood to include only testamentary heirs or both legal heirs and other prescribed heirs who also have the right to participate in the agreement to appoint an administrator of the worship estate. Although not clearly stated, if we refer to paragraph 3, Clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015, we can see that it seems that the legislators are in the direction that only the heirs according to the will have the right to agree to appoint a person to manage the estates used for worship. Because paragraph 3, Clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015 stipulates that, "In case all the heirs according to the will have died, the worship estate belongs to the person who is legally managing the property among those who are entitled to inherit according to the law". Specifically, in this case, there are still legal heirs, but the Civil Code 2015 does not allow legal heirs who are not designated by the testator to enjoy the inheritance in the will to agree to appoint a person to manage the worship estate, but in the direction that the estate used for worship belongs to the person who is legally managing it. The regulation that only testamentary heirs have the right to agree on appointing a person to manage the ancestral estate is not consistent with the reality in our country, specifically as follows:

First, the heir according to the will can be any individual, agency, or organization, and does not necessarily have to have a marriage, blood, or foster relationship with the person leaving the inheritance. Thus, the heir according to the will may not be a descendant or relative in the family. It is unreasonable to require outsiders who have nothing to do with the worship to participate in the agreement to appoint a person to manage the worship estate while the legal heirs are those who have the duty to worship and burn incense for their grandparents and parents but are not designated in the will and therefore cannot participate in the agreement to appoint a person to manage the worship estate.

Second, the worshipping inheritance is the part of the inheritance that is not divided among the heirs. Therefore, this part of the inheritance does not only belong to the heirs according to the will. Furthermore, for some reason, the testator only decides on a part of the inheritance in the will and therefore the part of the inheritance that is not decided in the will will be divided according to the law, so in addition to the heirs according to the will, there will also be the appearance of the heirs according to the law. For example, we have the following situation: Mr. A has a wife named B and five children named C, D, M, N, X. The estate left by Mr. A includes 3 houses and cash worth One billion dong. Mr. A made a will for C and D to receive cash worth one billion dong, leaving the house they are living in to

Mrs. B, one house for worship, and the other house not mentioned in the will. In this case, according to the Civil Code 2015, only C and D are named in the will, meaning that the heirs according to the will have the right to agree to appoint an administrator of the estate, which is not really reasonable. Because the house is an inheritance used for worship, it does not belong to the heirs according to the will, and in addition to the heirs according to the will, there are also legal heirs.

Third, according to Vietnamese tradition, worship is the duty of all children and grandchildren in the family and clan. According to custom, after the death of parents, on the anniversary day, children and grandchildren often gather in one place to pay respects and remember their grandparents and parents. This also contributes to tightening and consolidating the love and solidarity between brothers, children and relatives. The regulation that only heirs according to the will can agree to appoint an administrator of the inheritance is not suitable for practice in cases where the testator only designates a few of all children to receive a part of the inheritance. For example, the testator has a total of five children, but the testator only assigns a small part of the inheritance to two children and the ancestral estate, so the majority of the remaining inheritance will be divided according to the law among all five children. In this case, if only two children named in the will are entitled to agree to appoint an administrator of the ancestral estate, it may not be suitable for the majority of the remaining children's wishes. Meanwhile, worship is the duty of all children and according to tradition, on the anniversary day, all children and grandchildren gather at the place of worship to perform the anniversary. The appointment of an estate administrator based solely on the will of the heirs according to the will may not be agreed upon by the majority of the remaining people and thus the profound purpose of the law will not be achieved. Because, most of the brothers may not agree with the person appointed to manage the estate and thus they worship their father and mother at their own home instead of gathering at the place of worship. Not to mention the case where the estate administrator is at odds with the majority of the remaining brothers and sisters and therefore does not allow the brothers, sisters, children and grandchildren to come to the anniversary. Thus, the good purpose of the regulation on the inheritance of worship will not be fully achieved.

Second, Article 245 of the Civil Code 2015 has not clearly defined the rights and obligations of the manager of the worship heritage. Obviously, the manager of the worship heritage must also be responsible for preserving and maintaining the worship heritage to avoid damage, loss, or loss of value. The manager of the worship heritage is also not allowed to sell, exchange, pledge, mortgage, or perform other acts of disposal of the worship heritage. However, in addition to such rights and obligations, the manager of the worship heritage must also perform many other obligations in practice, and they must also spend money to preserve, maintain, and develop the heritage used for worship. For example, they manage an orchard and the harvested fruit will be used for annual offerings. However, to maintain that orchard, they must spend effort to fertilize, harvest, or they must spend money to repair and renovate the place of worship. And so, how will the efforts and expenses that the managers of the worship heritage have spent to preserve, maintain and develop the worship heritage be resolved? It is thought that the Civil Code 2015 needs to be amended and supplemented to more clearly stipulate the rights and obligations of the managers of the worship heritage.

Third, the worship heritage will be passed down for several generations and in case the manager of the worship heritage dies, which entity will continue to manage the worship heritage has not been specifically regulated. Obviously, in case the heirs of the person leaving the heritage are still alive, the heirs of the person leaving the worship heritage have the right to appoint another person to manage the worship heritage. However, in case all the heirs have died and the manager of the worship heritage also dies, how the right to manage the worship heritage will be transferred to the next generations has not been specifically regulated by law. Whether the right to manage the worship heritage will be transferred to the heirs of the manager of the worship heritage or all the grandchildren of the person leaving the worship heritage (ie the second-line heirs of the person leaving the heritage) will come forward to agree to appoint a new manager of the worship heritage. In addition, the Civil Code 2015 does not have clear regulations to determine how many generations the worship heritage will be passed down and how it will be handled when the worship ends.

4. Proposal to improve legal regulations on heritage used for worship

Based on the limitations and shortcomings identified above, we recommend perfecting the legal regulations on heritage used for worship as follows:

Firstly, amend and supplement paragraph 2, clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015 to clearly define the subject who has the right to agree to appoint a person to manage the worship estate. As analyzed in the limitations and shortcomings section, the Civil Code 2015 stipulates that in case the person leaving the inheritance does not appoint a person to manage the worship estate, the heirs shall appoint a person to manage the worship estate. However, the Civil Code 2015 has not clearly defined who the "heirs" are. Because the heirs include testamentary heirs and legal heirs. Testamentary heirs include ordinary testamentary heirs and legatees; legal heirs are divided into heirs according to the order of inheritance, successor heirs and inheritance between stepchildren and stepfathers and stepmothers. Meanwhile, paragraph 3 of Article 1 of the Civil Code 2015 stipulates that in case all the heirs according to the will have died, the worship estate belongs to the person who is legally managing the estate among those who are entitled to inherit according to the law. From the above provision, it can be seen that in the legislator's mind, only the heirs according to the will have the right to agree to appoint a person to manage the worship estate. Because the Civil Code 2015 stipulates that if all the heirs according to the will have died, the worship estate belongs to the legal manager, although there may still be legal heirs. The above provision is inappropriate because: First, the worship estate is the part of the estate that is not divided among the heirs, so the heirs have no right to this part of the estate. Second, the heirs according to the will may be a small number among the children of the person leaving the estate. Meanwhile, according to Vietnamese customs, worshipping the deceased is the obligation of all children and grandchildren in the family. Therefore, if only the heirs according to the will are allowed to agree to appoint a person to manage the inheritance used for worship, it may not be suitable for the wishes of all the children and grandchildren of the deceased. Therefore, we believe that paragraph 2, clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015 should be amended and supplemented as follows: "In case the person leaving the inheritance does not appoint a person to manage the inheritance for

worship, the legal heirs of the person leaving the inheritance shall agree to appoint a person to manage the inheritance for worship ". Thus, although the inheritance for worship is not divided, it belongs to the common rights of the legal heirs of the person leaving the inheritance and these people have the right to agree to appoint a person to manage the inheritance for worship. In principle, the person in the first line of inheritance will participate in the agreement to appoint a person to manage the inheritance for worship. If there is no one left in the first line of inheritance, the heirs in the second line of inheritance will agree to appoint a person to manage the inheritance for worship; if there is no one left in the first or second line of inheritance, the heirs in the third line of inheritance will agree to appoint a person to manage the inheritance used for worship. At the same time as amending and supplementing paragraph 2, clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015 as above, it is necessary to abolish paragraph 3, clause 1, Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015, because it is no longer necessary.

Second, it is necessary to supplement Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015 to clearly stipulate the issue of how many generations the worship heritage will be passed on and in case the person managing the heritage used for worship dies, to which entity will the right to manage the worship heritage be transferred? Because, according to the customs and practices of worship in Vietnam, the worship of grandparents, parents will be maintained through many generations. Previously, worship would be performed within five generations (Hanoi University of Law, 2014). However, today, worship is often only performed within three generations. Therefore, the author believes that the law needs to clearly stipulate that the worship heritage will be passed on within three generations, starting from the children of the person leaving the heritage. At the same time, the law also needs to specifically stipulate how to resolve the legal consequences of the heritage when the worship ends. In our opinion, the person managing the heritage used for worship has made contributions in taking care of, preserving and maintaining the heritage of worship, so when the last generation managing the heritage of worship dies, the heritage of worship will belong to their heirs.

In addition, the Civil Code 2015 also needs to specifically regulate the transfer of the right to manage the worship estate in the event that the manager of the worship estate dies or the manager of the worship estate fails to perform the worship obligation. In our opinion, the Civil Code needs to develop a separate law to regulate the issue of transferring the right to manage the portion of the estate used for worship. Accordingly, in the event that the person currently managing the worship estate dies, all legal heirs in the first line of the testator, including the successor, have the right to agree to appoint a person to manage the heritage used for worship. Because, in the event that the testator does not appoint a person to manage the heritage used for worship, the heir has the right to agree to appoint a person to manage the worship estate. Therefore, when the person designated in the will or the person agreed to be appointed by the heir as the manager of the estate dies, the heir of the testator has the right to agree to appoint a person to manage the estate. In case they have not agreed on an administrator of the inheritance, the inheritance will continue to be managed by the person currently possessing, using, and managing the inheritance. In case the second-generation inheritance administrator dies and there is no one left in the first generation, the second-generation heirs who are directly related to the testator have the

right to appoint a person to manage the ancestral inheritance. In case the second-generation heirs who are directly related to the testator do not appoint a person to manage the ancestral inheritance, the person currently possessing and managing the ancestral inheritance will continue to manage it. In case the third-generation inheritance administrator dies and there is no one left in the third generation, the ancestral inheritance will belong to the person currently possessing and managing the ancestral inheritance.

Third, the Civil Code 2015 needs to clearly stipulate the rights and obligations of the administrator of the worship estate. Article 645 of the Civil Code 2015 only stipulates in principle that in case the administrator of the worship estate does not properly execute the will or does not follow the agreement of the heirs, the heirs have the right to assign the portion of the estate used for worship to another person to manage. With this provision, if the will or the agreement appointing the administrator of the worship estate clearly stipulates the duties and powers, it will be more convenient to determine the obligations and rights of the administrator of the worship estate. But if the above documents do not stipulate the rights and obligations of the administrator of the worship estate, how will their rights and obligations be determined? As analyzed in the legal shortcomings, in addition to the obligation to preserve the heritage and perform worship, in the process of managing the heritage of worship, many issues may arise that need to be resolved, such as: the costs and efforts they spend to preserve and develop the heritage used for worship. For example, if there is an orchard used for worship, the heritage manager must fertilize, weed, prune, kill insects, harvest fruit... then how will the costs and efforts they spend be calculated? Therefore, the Civil Code 2015 needs to develop a separate regulation to specify in detail the rights and obligations of the manager of the heritage of worship. Specifically, we can develop a separate law regulating the rights and obligations of the manager of the heritage used for worship in the following direction:

“Article...Obligations and rights of the administrator of the heritage used for worship.

1. The administrator of the portion of the inheritance used for worship has the following obligations:

a. Must preserve the heritage used for worship; must not sell, exchange, donate, mortgage, pledge or perform other acts of disposal on the heritage used for worship;

b. The profits and income obtained from the exploitation and use of worship heritage may only be used for worship purposes after deducting the expenses incurred to exploit, use and preserve the heritage.

c. Notify heirs of the status of the ancestral estate.

d. Compensate for damages if the administrator of the heritage used for worship violates his/her obligations and causes damage;

2. The administrator of the portion of the inheritance used for worship has the following rights:

a. Possess and use the heritage used for worship according to the provisions of the will or according to the agreement of the legal heirs.

b. To request the legal heirs of the testator to pay the expenses incurred to preserve the worship heritage;

c. In case the estate manager exploits and uses the heritage used for worship and generates profits or income, he/she shall be entitled to a portion of the profits or income or a portion of the value of the profits or income”.

With specific regulations on the rights and obligations of the manager of the inheritance used for worship, it helps the subjects related to the inheritance of worship know how to behave appropriately and also creates a legal basis for the Court in resolving inheritance disputes in general and disputes related to the management of inheritance used for worship in particular.

5. Conclusion

Worship is a good cultural feature in Vietnamese society and leaving behind heritage for worship is a practice in Vietnam and is recognized in the Civil Code of Vietnam. The article has researched and clarified the concept of heritage for worship and the current status of Vietnamese law on heritage for worship. Through the research of the article, we have analyzed and clarified the limitations and inadequacies in the legal regulations on heritage for worship in Vietnam and at the same time made recommendations to improve the provisions of the law.

6. References

1. Civil Code 2015
2. Do Van Dai (2019), Vietnamese Inheritance Law - Judgments and Judgment Commentaries, Volume 1, Hong Duc Publishing House - Vietnam Lawyers Association, Ho Chi Minh City, P.688.
3. Hoang The Lien (2013), Scientific commentary on the Civil Code 2015, Volume 3, National Political Publishing House, Hanoi, P. 92.
4. Le Minh Hung (2020), Ten problems related to the statute of limitations for inheritance according to the provisions of the Civil Code 2015, Scientific conference documents: Statute of limitations in Vietnamese civil law, Ho Chi Minh City University of Law, P. 83.
5. Nguyen Van Huy (2017), Inheritance in Vietnamese civil law, Hanoi Justice Publishing House, P. 83
6. Nguyen Van Cu - Tran Thi Hue (2017), Scientific commentary on the Civil Code 2015, People's Police Publishing House, Hanoi, P. 963.
7. Pham Van Tuyet (2007), Inheritance - Legal regulations and application practices , National Political Publishing House, Hanoi, P. 95-96.
8. Hanoi Law University (2014) Textbook of History of State and Law of Vietnam , People's Police Publishing House, Hanoi, P. 225.
9. Ho Chi Minh City University of Law (2023), Law on property, ownership and inheritance , Hong Duc Publishing House, Ho Chi Minh City, P.538.